

CARBON NANOTUBES FOR *IN SITU* THERMOMECHANICAL AND THERMOCHEMICAL SENSING IN COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Over the past 15+ years there has been a large focus on the research and development of carbon nanotube-reinforced composites. Because the carbon nanotubes are much smaller than conventional advanced fibers it has been shown that nanotubes can be used to modify matrix-dominated properties of fiber reinforced composite materials, including in-plane and interlaminar properties [1]. Initially, it was expected that the extremely large aspect ratio and high axial strength and stiffness of nanotubes would result in a dramatic increase in mechanical properties of composites. However, only matrix dominated mechanical properties were improved to a significant degree [2, 3].

One of their most unique properties is the formation of electrically conductive networks at low carbon nanotube concentrations, often below 0.1 wt% of carbon nanotubes. Nanotubes have a high current carrying capacity and an inherent mixture of metallic and semiconductor-like electrical behavior originating from their atomic structure and layering (as in the case of multi-walled nanotubes). More passive uses, such as electromagnetic shielding and increased electrical/thermal conductivity, were of initial interest. This unique ability to form networks has enabled their use as materials where their piezoresistivity – the change of electrical properties with applied deformation that is higher than expected based on simple dimensional changes – can be exploited in sensing applications.

Thostenson *et al.* [4] developed approaches for *in situ* sensing of microcracks using a percolating network of nanotubes in fiber-reinforced composites. A combination of linear and non-linear piezoresistive behavior was observed, with the non-linearity resulting from the formation of matrix cracks. The damage sensing functionality has its

origins in the changes occurring in the carbon nanotube interphase, or the nanotube/nanotube tunneling junctions in the percolating networks [5].

Current methods of monitoring the health of critical structures and components, such as c-scan non-destructive evaluation (NDE), typically cannot be used during service. This greatly limits their effectiveness in tracking damage growth and predicting failure. There is a need to implement real-time *in situ* sensing technologies which are scalable and non-detrimental to the structure, giving real-time information to users/operators in order to improve safety and reliability. In addition to structural health monitoring based on the sensing of deformation and cracking, we have recently explored other sensing capabilities of nanotube-based composites using electrical resistance measurement and high-frequency time-domain reflectometry (TDR). It was shown in [6-9] that these methods are effective in sensing temperature, polymer mobility and other thermomechanical processes.

In this research, we evaluate the thermoresistive behavior of carbon nanotube composites for sensing of resin cure as well as thermomechanical changes that occur during in-service exposure to extreme temperatures. Since the nanocomposite bulk resistivity is dominated by the tunneling resistance at nanotube/nanotube junctions the nanotubes effectively act as a network of sensors that can detect thermal transitions and other thermochemical changes *in situ*. Electrical resistance and TDR measurements were made *in situ* during several experimental techniques in order to correlated signal change to intrinsic material changes. These included thermomechanical analysis (TMA), torsional braid analysis (TBA), combined mechanical/thermal cycling, and various loading regimes (tensile, shear, etc.). The data shows that the sensing is based on the

tunneling of electrons through a thin polymer interface between individual nanotubes dispersed in the material (Figure 1). The resulting percolating network of nano-scale sensors return powerful information originating from changes in the local electrical properties.

Fig.1. Illustration showing tunneling of electrons between nanotubes dispersed in a polymer matrix.

2 Materials

2.1 Material Synthesis and Functionalization

The polymer matrix systems studied in this work are all thermosetting vinyl ester resins. Vinyl ester resins are commonly used in a variety of industrial applications because of their low viscosity and tailorable curing characteristics which make them suitable for many out-of-autoclave resin infusion processes. Commercial vinyl ester (VE) resins are available as blends of VE monomer and styrene monomer. This limits their processability in some mixing operations because of the high volatility of the styrene component. For this reason, the VE resins used with carbon nanotubes in this work were synthesized in-house from a bisphenol-F type epoxy monomer (EPON Resin 862, Momentive, USA) and methacrylic acid with triphenylphosphine and triphenylantimony (III) (99 %, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) as catalysts at 0.25 and 0.75 wt%, respectively.

A batch of 100 g epoxy was reacted at 90 to 95 °C while stirring for 2 hr and allowed to cool to room temperature. As shown in Figure 2, the esterification reaction involves the opening of the epoxy ring groups and subsequent termination with the ester groups forming VE monomer. Styrene monomer (≥ 99 %, ReagentPlus, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was mixed in at a later stage at 40 wt%. Immediately prior to vacuum infusion or casting, the accelerator (6 % cobalt naphthenate in mineral spirits, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and curing agent (Trigonox 239, AzkoNobel, USA) were added at 0.2 and 1 wt%, respectively.

For larger-scale composites that did not require direct carbon nanotube dispersion a commercial vinyl ester resin was used (Derakane® 501A-40, Ashland Inc.). Two different initiator/accelerator combinations were used for fast and slow curing. (1) 2% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (Chemtura Inc.) as the accelerator and 0.3% Cobalt-Naphthenate (6% Cobalt, Mahagony Co.) as initiator; (2) Derakane 501A-40 with 1.5% Trigonox® 311 (AkzoNobel) as the accelerator, 0.2% Cobalt-Naphthenate as initiator and 0.5% Acetyl Acetone (0.05%) as an inhibitor.

In some cases, it was necessary to functionalize the nanotubes to make them more compatible with the matrix resin system. Carbon nanotubes (CM-95, Hanwha Nanotech, Korea) were oxidized in a dilute solution of ultra-pure deionized water (1 g/L CNT concentration) while undergoing ultrasonication and ozoneolysis using a previously developed method [9]. A peristaltic pump (MU-D01, Major Science, USA) was used to circulate the CNT solution through a sonicator cell (Sonicator 3000, Misonix, with 800B Floccell, Qsonica, USA) and into an Erlenmeyer flask with ozone gas bubbler. Ozone gas was produced by corona discharge with an oxygen-fed ozone generator (1000BT-12, Taoture International Enterprises Inc, China). Both the sonication cell and Erlenmeyer flask were maintained at 5°C. Using previous x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) results of An and co-workers [9], the treatment time of six hours resulted in an oxygen-to-carbon ratio of about 0.09, versus 0.02 for untreated CNT.

2.2 Composites Manufacturing

To manufacture structural composites with CNTs and bulk nanocomposite samples, a calendaring

method was used to disperse nanotubes in the resin. Calendering requires the use of stable non-volatile mixing media because of the high surface area to mixing-volume ratio involved. For this reason, CNTs were dispersed in VE monomer and not the VE/styrene blends available commercially. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the 3-roll-mill calendaring apparatus used to disperse CNTs (EXAKT 80E, EXAKT Technologies, USA) and lists the key processing parameters (roller speeds and gap settings). The process involved passing a batch of 80 to 120 g VE monomer/CNT mixture from the collector plate back to the material feed section while periodically decreasing the roller gap settings. This procedure results in a high dispersion of CNTs in the VE monomer [10]. The styrene monomer was mixed in at 40 wt% using a hand-held homogenizer (Tissuemiser Homogenizer, Fisher Scientific, USA). Final CNT concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 1 wt% were prepared using this method.

To manufacture very small samples of resin (~ 10 g) with CNT concentrations ranging from 0.1 wt% to 1 wt%, oxidized CNTs were extracted from the aqueous solution prepared using the procedure in Section 2.1 using electrophoretic deposition (EPD). An electric field strength of about 30 V/cm was applied for 2 hr between stainless steel electrode plates. This caused the CNTs to collect onto the electrode plates and fall out of solution. The product was collected and dried overnight on a hot plate at 80 °C. A 50 % yield of the original CNT mass was achieved. To disperse the oxidized nanotubes in vinyl ester resin, the CNTs, with a few drops of styrene monomer, were briefly milled in a mortar and pestle to break apart the wafer-like product into smaller agglomerates. This paste was then added to the VE and styrene mixture and placed in a sonication bath (Branson 1510, Emerson Industrial Automation, USA) for 3 h.

To fabricate structural composites with glass fiber reinforcement, a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process was used. The VARTM process can be used to fabricate large complex geometry parts and is well suited for laboratory scale manufacturing. It is a low-cost method which can

Fig. 2. Schematic of 3-roll-mill showing key parameters of the high shear mixing process [10].

be used with a variety of tooling surfaces, including the “smart tooling” described in later sections. The cure cycle was 12+ hr at room temperature, followed by 2 hr at 165°C. This cure cycle determined from a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study [11] to give a complete reaction of the vinyl ester and styrene monomers.

3. Nanotube-Based Tunneling for Sensing

3.1 Thermochemical Response During Cure

Considering the sensitivity to polymer relaxation processes observed during thermoresistive analysis [6], it was expected that the technique could be adapted to monitor the cure process. To evaluate the thermochemical sensing performance of CNT/VE nanocomposites, a specialized test was designed based on torsional braid analysis (TBA) with *in situ* electrical resistance measurement. In TBA, a glass fiber braid is saturated with liquid resin and viscoelastic changes are measured during cure. The key advantage of TBA over other techniques is that the specimen may be studied continuously through all material states and transformations. A rheometer (AR-2000, TA Instruments, USA) with solid geometry torsion accessory was used as an analog for the torsion pendulum used in traditional TBA tests (See Fig. 3) [12]. Electrical resistance was measured *in situ* along the length of the specimen using a custom data acquisition system. Isothermal

Fig. 3. Image of TBA set-up; AR-2000 rheometer with torsion accessory attached with 0.1 wt% nanotube/VE specimen mounted.

and temperature ramp segments were run at 0.0314 rad displacement at 1 Hz with ramping rates of 2 °C/min and a normal force of 0.5 N (+/- 0.3 N) tension. Specimens were cured under isothermal or continuous heating conditions, followed by a post cure step. All testing profiles were terminated with thermal cycles in order to measure the thermochemical and viscoelastic trends following the curing steps.

The results for a 0.50 wt% nanotube/VE specimen undergoing continuous heating cure are presented in Fig. 4. Delta, the phase lag between the storage and loss moduli, is plotted along with the normalized electrical resistance. During continuous heating cure, the resin experiences multiple transformations which are indicated by local maxima and minima in the delta versus temperature curve. Overall, electrical resistance appears to follow the degree of cure, where vitrification results in a large increase in resistance. Once the T_g is exceeded, the cross-linking reaction can continue further in the rubber state. This trend is apparent for the post-cure step as well. As apparent in Fig. 5, there is a diffusion-like increase in electrical resistance with time. This is a significant observation since the later stages of cure are known to proceed in a diffusion-controlled manner [11].

Fig. 4. Thermochemical / viscoelastic response of a nanocomposite undergoing continuous heating cure during torsional braid analysis; key material transitions denoted by the dashed lines.

Fig. 5. Electrical resistance curve of a nanocomposite during the post-cure step at 165 °C following continuous heating cure; showing diffusion-like increase in resistance.

3.2 Thermoresistive/Thermochemical Response

Combined thermoresistive / thermomechanical analysis was conducted using a thermomechanical analyzer (TMA) (TMA/SDTA841e, Mettler Toledo, USA) with a multifunctional data acquisition device (NI-6218, National Instruments, USA) controlled

using customized LabVIEW software and an external PC. Nanocomposite specimens were designed specifically to meet the requirements of the TMA and to accommodate an *in situ* electrical resistance measurement. Fig. 6 shows the test configuration where the electrical resistance is measured along the length of the specimen and the TMA probe measures thermal expansion in the thickness direction, h , shown in normalized form by $\Delta h/h_0$ in %. Specimens were subjected to several thermal cycles between 25 and 165°C at a ramp rate of 3°C/min. Electrical resistance is represented in normalized form by $\Delta R/R_0$ in %.

Fig 6. Photograph of nanocomposite specimen mounted on the TMA stage for thermoresistive / thermomechanical characterization.

The characteristic thermoresistive response for a CNT/VE nanocomposite with CNT concentration well above the percolation threshold is shown in Fig. 7. In the temperature range from 25 to 165 °C, there are two local maxima observed. The local minimum separating these peaks corresponds directly to the glass transition temperature (T_g). Fig. 8 clearly shows the direct correlation between sensing of T_g by the thermoresistive and thermomechanical methods by simultaneous measurement. It is interesting to compare this multi-peak behavior to curves produced by the thermally stimulated discharge current method (TSD) and dielectric constant analysis for the vinyl ester system [13]. In TSD, the release of trapped charge carriers during the relaxation of specific polymer segments or side

chains results in a local maxima in discharge current [14]. The similarity indicates that the electron tunneling between CNTs acts much like a nanoscale electrothermic sensor, capable of sensing polymer relaxation processes.

Fig. 7. Electrical resistance during prolonged thermal cycling - note that the transient trend in resistance is due to permanent increases in resistance at the 165 °C set point [6].

Fig. 8. Thermal expansion and electrical resistance curves showing direct agreement between thermoresistive and thermomechanical sensing of glass transition.

3.3 Sensing of Structural Composites under Combined Loading

To test the damage sensing and thermomechanical / thermoresistive sensing performance of structural composites under extreme environments, cross-ply composites of glass fiber and dispersed CNTs in vinyl ester resin were tested under a combined thermal and mechanical loading condition. The electrical resistance of the specimens was monitored *in situ* and in real-time using a data acquisition system. Tabbed specimens were placed in a constant displacement weathering fixture originally design by NASA for evaluating the performance of polymer composites at cryogenic temperatures [15], and pre-strained to approximately 1300 $\mu\epsilon$ then placed inside an environmental testing chamber (Z8-Plus, Cincinnati Sub-Zero, USA) and cycled using the maximum performance limitations of the chamber. The thermal cycling profile consisted of 30 minute isothermal segments for the temperature extremes of 150 and -73 and also 25°C.

The electrical resistance response for a cross-ply glass fiber composite with 0.75 wt% CNT content under the combined thermal / mechanical loading conditions is shown in Fig. 9. The trend shows an apparent negative temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR), whereas the 0.75 wt% CNT/VE nanocomposite has an overall positive TCR. This is because of the competing coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the glass reinforcement fibers and polymer matrix which causes the matrix to be in compression when the temperature is increased. Fig. 10 shows electrical resistance vs. temperature for the final thermal cycle illustrates this principle where the increase in matrix CTE during T_g results in an increasingly negative TCR. The transient decrease in resistance was due to stress relaxation which occurred during the first few thermal cycles when T_g was exceeded. In addition to the inherent damage sensing functionality of the composite, this work demonstrates the ability to sense the matrix stress state and glass transition *in situ* under combined loading.

Fig. 9. Electrical resistance response to thermal cycling while constrained in a constant displacement weather fixture; dashed lines show maximum and minimum temperature contours and average 25 °C contour.

Fig. 10. Electrical resistance change during the final thermal cycle iteration; slope change around 100 °C attributed to increase in matrix CTE during the glass transition.

4. Time Domain Reflectometry Based Sensing

Electric time domain reflectometry (TDR) refers to a process of sending a high frequency voltage pulse through a transmission line [7-8]. Electrical discontinuities along the transmission line result in reflections and the time difference between the

incident and reflected waveforms is used to calculate the position of the discontinuity. An application of the TDR technique to sense flow during composites manufacturing is illustrated in Fig. 11. During resin flow through a preform, the flow front acts as an electrical discontinuity and hence the reflection from the flow front can be analyzed to calculate the location of the resin. Using the TDR technique, multi-point sensing can be implemented using only a single transmission line and the procedure is suitable for monitoring flow fronts during the fabrication of large composite parts.

Fig. 11. TDR for flow sensing.

4.1 TDR for Thermochemical Sensing

Curing of resin is a thermochemical process and the dielectric constant of the resin changes with cure state. Time domain reflectometry can be used to monitor this impedance change and hence can be used to estimate the cure state of the resin. An experimental setup to monitor cure state of the resin is shown in Fig. 12. The electromagnetic fields around the TDR sensor are shown in Fig. 13 and the experimental results are shown in Fig. 14 for a slow-curing vinyl ester resin system. There is a direct correlation between the impedance change and the DSC results.

Fig. 12. TDR based cure monitoring.

Fig. 13. Electric fields (red) and magnetic fields (green) around the TDR sensor.

Fig. 14. Comparison of cure monitoring data obtained from DSC and TDR for Derakane with Trigonox (1.5%) as curing agent, Cobalt-Naphthenate (0.2%) as initiator and Acetyl Acetone (0.05%) as inhibitor.

4.2 TDR for Damage Sensing

Similar to cure monitoring, TDR sensors can be used for damage sensing of composites as well. Fig. 15 shows the sensor design concept for TDR based damage sensing and Fig 16 shows experimental results. Our researches [8,16] have shown that TDR can be successfully used for sensing damage in both unidirectional and cross ply laminates. The micro-crack damage in cross ply laminates can be

monitored if the composites are modified with CNTs in damage prone region [16]. This is because the CNT networks have coupled electromagnetic-mechanical properties and are damaged during micro-cracking. The damage is picked up in form of TDR impedance change.

Fig. 15. TDR based damage sensing concept.

Fig. 16. Experimental results for TDR based damage sensing of unidirectional laminates.

5. Conclusions

The electrical properties of carbon nanotube-based composites can be exploited in a variety of multifunctional applications. We have demonstrated that the electrical properties of carbon nanotube composites can be utilized to sense the cure state and also thermomechanical and thermochemical changes in the polymer system. Since the nanocomposite bulk resistivity is dominated by the tunneling resistance at nanotube/nanotube junctions the nanotubes effectively act as a network of sensors that can detect mechanical and chemical changes *in*

situ. Changes in high-frequency impedance can also be utilized to sense cure and damage state.

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